

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B038
 Date: 01 Aug 2004
 Take Off: 08:59:33
 Landing: 14:14:27
 Flight Time: 5h14m54

Trials Instructions: ITOP – Fourth interception of low level WCB, directly beneath forest fire emissions mixed into air of both tropospheric and stratospheric origin

Operating Area: Northeast of Faial (area booked for 41-47N, 19-27W, surface to FL250)

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Foster	Directflight
3	Mission Scientist 1	John Methven	Reading University
4	Flight Manager	Maureen Smith	FAAM
5	Core Chemistry/FWVS/CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
6	HCHO	Graham Mills	UEA
7	PTR-MS	Anne Hulse	UEA
8	PERCA	Alex Parker	Leicester University
9	Peroxides	Brian Bandy	UEA
10	FAGE	Trevor Ingham	Leeds University
11	PAN/ORAC	Lisa Whalley	Leeds University
12	WAS	Nicola Watson	York University
13	AMS	Jonny Crosier	UMIST
14	NOxy	Dave Stewart	UEA
15	Mission Scientist 2	Ruth Purvis	York University
16	Observer	Jana Slemr	UEA
17	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
18			

Track Plot:

B038 Track 01-AUG-04

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B038
 Date: 1st August 2004
 Project: ITOP Triple Decker
 Location: Azores, N of ANAVA

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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085933		T/O	5.4 kft	078	from Horta
090740	091046	Run 1	11.0 kft	056	Wet chem checks
091832		Event 1	16.5 kft	057	in climb to FL170
091920	092505	Run 2	17.0 kft	056	
092506	093050	Profile 1	17.0 - 22.9 kft	056	1000fpm
092628		Videos	18.3 kft	057	Start recording
093732	093955	Profile 1	23.0 - 25.0 kft	043	Interrupt for ATC
095327		Event 2	25.0 kft	026	Position report
102005	102852	Profile 2	25.0 - 17.0 kft	016	
102904	104911	Run 3	17.0 kft	017	Interrupt P2 for NOXY Cals
104911	105821	Profile 2	17.0 - 7.2 kft	017	
105935	110150	Profile 2	7.2 - 4.8 kft	020	1000fpm
110159	110822	Profile 2	4.7 - 1.1 kft	017	500fpm from FL50
110923	111602	Profile 3	1.1 - 5.0 kft	076	500fpm 500fpm to FL50
111603	112353	Profile 3	5.1 - 12.9 kft	072	500fpm to FL50
112547	113110	Profile 4	13.0 - 8.7 kft	243	1000fpm
113118	113534	Run 4	8.6 kft	259	
113535	113756	Profile 5	8.6 - 7.2 kft	258	get back into layer
113756	114650	Run 4	7.2 - 8.1 kft	255	
114741	120528	Profile 6	8.6 - 24.9 kft	204	
120640	121357	Run 5	25.0 kft	206	
121358	122232	Profile 7	25.0 - 16.1 kft	206	1000fpm
122232	124248	Run 6	16.1 - 16.0 kft	206	
122920		Videos	16.0 kft	205	Change tapes
124248	125628	Profile 8	16.0 - 5.0 kft	206	
125628	130557	Profile 9	5.0 - 14.0 kft	203	
130557	132346	Run 7	14.0 kft	205	
133500		Event 3	14.0 kft	244	Position report
140229	140430	Run 8	7.1 kft	257	Abeam Pico
141427		Land	-.06 kft	089	At Horta

B038 Track 01-AUG-04

25W

20W

SHANNON CONTROL
131.15
135.60
(SOTA)

SHANNON OCEANIC
TRANSITION AREA (SOTA) (A)
FL 55

BEDRA
N49 00.0
W015 00.0

TAKAS N49 00.0 W008 00.0	ALUTA N49 00.3 W007 29.9	MOSIS N49 00.4 W007 12.9 (On request UN-491)
095° UN 491	20	11
RATKA N49 30.0 W008 00.0 (On request EGTT)	LARLA N49 22.7 W007 07.3	DEKOR N49 10.2 W006 26.9 [LND66]
108° UN 512	35 288	29 23
LASNO N48 35.9 W009 00.0	46 244	TAKAS N49 00.0 W008 00.0
064° UT 86		GAPLI N50 00.0 W008 00.0
030° UT 8	E> 93 211	

For flights entering the Shannon OCA directly from the Shannon Oceanic Transition Area (SOTA), the designated entry points are SOMAX, BEDRA, OMOKO or LASNO. For flights entering the Shannon Oceanic Transition Area (BOTA), the designated entry points are ETIKI, SEPAL or SVIR.

NAT TRACKS TO LISBON AIRPORT
NAT tracks are anchored on Espichel VORTAC and Santiago VORDME. tributary tracks via DIRMA Int will be cleared. All operators conducting flight operations in the Santa Maria OCA north of 37°N shall provide information to Santa Maria OAC regarding the tracks likely to be requested during the peak traffic periods.

SHANNON OCEANIC CTA (A) / EGGX FIR
(Unc't 1 Below FL55)
NAT-RVSM AIRSPACE FL290-FL410

SANTA MARIA OCEANIC CTA (A) / LPPO FIR (G)
(Unc't 1 below FL55)
NAT-RVSM AIRSPACE FL290-FL410

+2 = UTC +1 = UTC

SANTA MARIA RADIO

NAT A	NAT E
3016	2962
5598	6628
8906	8825
13506	11309
17946	17946

VHF 127.90 132.07
SELCAL
① 426302

① SATCOM Air-to-Ground COM-failure.

ORTIS N31 24.4 W016 33.4	273	210°
DEGUN N35 25.1 W015 39.5	53	032°
RULET N34 15.1 W014 54.9	146	053°
IBIDO N40 55.1 W010 11.2	31	099°
TELAMU N35 38.3 W014 31.8	621	210°
ROLAR N34 12.7 W015 12.3	11 E	032°
NARTA N36 05.4 W012 33.5	745	053°
DIRMA N40 51.1 W009 30.1	975	053°
	27	099°

SANTA MARIA CONTROL
132.15 (TMA)
Above FL 155

FL285 TMA (A)
(Below FL 195(C))

SANTA MARIA

DOKAS
N37 13.9
W023 21.9

BEKUN
N37 56.9
W023 14.1

BAVAS
N39 00.0
W023 40.7

ANAVA
N39 54.0
W025 24.5

LAJES

HORTA

GOMOS
N37 00.8
W030 03.4

GINSU
N36 17.5
W027 38.9

ETROX
N36 24.2
W024 01.5

A(H)1

SANTA MARIA OCEANIC CTA (A) / LPPO FIR (G)
(Unc't 1 below FL55)
NAT-RVSM AIRSPACE FL290-FL410

IRKID
N33 55.5
W018 04.3

PELUS
N35 31.2
W016 14.4

40000g
00g @ 1100g
110000g

41N 27W

SFC-FL 250
41N 19W

OTF STILL AIR
6000W
5000M

OTF STILL AIR
4000M

AZORES +1 = UTC
(SUMMER = UTC)

+1 = UTC
+2 = UTC

B038 ITOP – “The Last Bite at the Triple Decker”.
**Fourth interception of low level WCB, directly beneath forest fire emissions mixed
into air of both tropospheric and stratospheric origin.**

Mission Scientists: John Methven & Ruth Purvis

Date: 01/08/04

Outline schedule:

05:00 UT - Power to aircraft - Warm-up
07:00 UT - Air Crew Briefing
08:15 UT – Security sweep
08:30 UT – Boarding deadline
09:00 UT - Take-off

Location: Northeast of Faial (area booked for 41-47N, 19-27W, surface-FL250).

Aim: Low level pollution was sampled by the P3 as it moved along the US East Coast on the 27 and 28 July. Pollutant signal was lost rapidly during the first day through mixing with maritime air. It was intercepted again by the BA146 on 31 July. Also on the 28 July the P3 intercepted a forest fire plume (from Northern Canada) that clearly showed mixing with stratospheric air on its upper edge. Similar signatures were seen by the BA146 on 31 July. Today’s flight aims to intersect all three airmasses sampled by the P3 as they are strung out along a cold front. Mixing is expected between the layers induced by the shear flow.

Sortie Detail

1. T+0 Take Off. Ascend to first available level for wet chemistry checks. (10)
2. T+10 Ascend to FL170 and fly to Anava. Include at least 20 mins level in clear air (if possible) for calcs. (35)
3. T+45 Profile ascent @1000ft/min to FL250 and head towards WCB target at 220 knots (45.5N, 22W). (60)
4. T+105 Profile descent @1000ft/min (500ft/min below 5000ft) to 500ft or lowest attainable level (cloud likely) to reach target point. (30) ^{1000ft.}
5. T+135 Profile ascent @500ft/min to FL090 towards ENE (to 46N, 20W). (20)
6. T+155 Turn SW (parallel to cold front) and level run @FL090 (may drop slightly into chosen layer) for 12 minutes. (15)
7. T+170 Profile ascent @1000ft/min to FL220 looking for levels of fire plume, stratospheric signature and mid-west pollution above and into cleaner air. (15)
8. T+185 Profile descent @1000ft/min to level of fire plume CO maximum. (10)
9. T+195 Level run within plume maximum for 12 minutes. (15)
10. T+210 Profile ascent @500ft/min into stratospheric influence. (5)
11. T+215 Level run within air mass for 12 minutes (approx FL140) (now roughly at 42.5N, 25W). (15)
12. T+230 Head for Anava (may profile up or down while north of 41N). (40)
13. T+270 Head for Faial @FL140. (40)
14. T+310 Racetrack next to NNE side of Pico if cloud free. (15)
15. T+325 Land.

New plot, same times

Flight B038 13:00:41

Heading 205 deg Speed 243 knots Height 8.7kft Press 731mb

Lat 41.4N Long 24.8W Wind 10 ms-1/ 300 deg

Temp 8.37C Dewpoint -7.76C

From 11:00:00 to now

—	Current values			
—	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	46839	secs	⊙ All
—	RELATIVE HUMIDITY	77.11	%	⊙
—	OZONE MIXING RATIO	64.25	ppb	⊙
—	PRESSURE HEIGHT	8.76	Kft	⊙
—	CO MIXING RATIO	139.05	ppb	⊙

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B.038**.....

Date **1.8.04**.....

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU			<u>Probes</u>		
GPS		/	FFSSP	X	
Satcom C			PCASP	X	
Satcom H		✓	2D-P	X	
<u>Thermometers</u>			2D-C	X	
De-Iced Temp			Cloudscope	X	
Non De-Iced			SID 1	X	
Heimann		/	SID 2	X	
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CPI		
G. Eastern			HVPS		
J. Williams			<u>Racks:</u>		
Nevzorov			INC	X	
TWC			CCN / CNC		FWVS
FWVS		/	CVI	X	
<u>Radiometers</u>			<u>Aerosol</u>		
Upper Clear			PSAP		✓
“ Red			Nephelometer	X	
“ Silicon JWB2			AMS		✓
“ JO1D					
Lower Clear					
“ Red					
“ Silicon JWB2					
“ JO1D		/			
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	X				
MARSS	X				
DEIMOS	X				
ARIES	X				
SWS / SHIM	X				
<u>Chemistry</u>					
Ozone					
ECGC					
NOX					
CO			<u>Others:</u>		
ORAC					
PAN					
PERCA					
WAS		/			

Flight Manager's Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. 6038 1.8.04

Instruments

1. Upper chr BBR reading -180, red +105! Seems to have the right signal structure, just with a huge negative offset. Climbed to 610 W/m² in flight (red 283 W/m²)
2. TWC - all channels to 2046 on sw on, then okay
3. Lost science power during pwr clo - NOXY will need about 1 hr from now to stabilise again.
4. HORACE - NOT receiving DRS data, status message for H-DRS-LOG all indications are that data is being recvd and recorded.
5. Rear Facing Camera - had a picture initially but lost it towards end of preflight.
6. Aft Car Con display - ie windows bombed out during flight
7. HORACE Update FLT summ - when selecting combined event
↳ eg end run + start profile, any comments are repeated in both lines
↳ Also, add posn of cursor on graph plots in calibrated (no scale) data.
8. FM PC - display locked up, had to reboot pc.
9. Printer - black cartridge low error message on Aft Car Con pc - plots okay.
10. Upper Red BBR - spikes on data 1257 to 1310

BBRs - are they getting cleaned?

Aircraft

check Ozone constants in Floods:fltcons against hor-calib.dat.